

Writer

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I believe in my ambition,
Because I consider it my mission.
I was born to have this passion,
And so should my mind and heart be in cooperation.
Being a keen observer is the first step.
Faith and dedication should always be adept
My paper and pen will be my weapons
So that my abstract ideas will be dynamic, just like crayons.
I want you to know my loudest dream,
Which nobody can destroy or dim.
I want to express and speak through letters,
I want to be a writer, now and forever.